

NOTES

Spectrophotometric Study of Uranium (VI) Complexes of N-Hydroxysuccinamic Acid

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A large number of hydroxamic acids have been investigated in the past 15 years for the detection, separation and determination of a number of metal ions. Important amongst these are : benzohydroxamic acid¹, N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid², salicylhydroxamic acid³, oxaldihydroxamic acid⁴, nicotinohydroxamic acid⁵, quinaldinohydroxamic acid⁶, 2-naphthohydroxamic acid⁷ and thiophene-2-hydroxamic acid⁸. Bass and Yoe⁹ have recently examined the reactions of 33 hydroxamic acids and 3 N-substituted hydroxamic acids. A survey of the literature revealed that despite the ever increasing interest in hydroxamic acids, N-hydroxysuccinamic acid (HOOC-CH₂CH₂-CO-NH-OH) seems to have not drawn attention so far. A few references occur in the literature describing its physiological activities¹⁰. Hence, it was considered worthwhile to study the chelating properties of this compound with different metal ions. It offers some advantages over other hydroxamic acids. Firstly, it can be prepared easily from ordinary laboratory chemicals and secondly it is soluble in water and gives water-soluble coloured metal complexes, thus making it a suitable reagent for the spectrophotometric work.

It gives water-soluble coloured complexes with iron (III), manganese (II), titanium (IV), vanadium (V), molybdenum (VI), uranium (VI) etc. In the present communication its reactions with uranium (VI) are described. In the pH range between 2.0 and 7.5 it gives an orange complex and between 7.5 and 10.0, a yellow complex. The former complex has been examined in detail because of its greater stability than the latter.

Preparation of the compound : The method given by Hurd *et al.*¹¹ for preparing N-hydroxysuccinamic acid was adopted by us with a slight modification. Instead of sodium ethoxide recommended by them, methanolic solution of potassium hydroxide has been employed. The method consists in reacting hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.67 mole) with methylhydrogen succinate (0.33 mole) in presence of potassium hydroxide (2 mole) in methanol. Potassium chloride formed is filtered and the filtrate left at the room temperature for crystallisation. Di-potassium salt of N-hydroxysuccinamic acid comes out in the form of white crystals in about six hours. It melts with decomposition at 200°. Found : C, 22.79; N, 6.61%. Calculated : C, 22.96; N, 6.69%.

It is highly soluble in water, very slightly so in alcohol and insoluble in organic solvents. In solid state it is stable but in solution it deteriorates in about 10 hours giving a light greenish product. Its aqueous solution shows a steep fall in the ultra violet region and has no absorption in the visible region.

Absorbance curves : A Beckman spectrophotometer, Model DU, was used for absorbance measurements. pH was measured with a Cambridge bench type pH meter. 2.5 ml of uranyl nitrate solution containing 500 ppm of the metal were taken separately in a number of 25-ml flasks and 2.5 ml of 1 *M* KCl and 5 ml of ligand solutions were added to each. Suitable amounts of 1% sodium hydroxide and 10% hydrochloric acid solutions were added so that the pH of the final solutions ranged between 1.5 and 10.5. The volume was made upto the mark. These solutions corresponded to 50 ppm of uranium. Absorbance was taken after 20 min. at different wave-lengths, using water as blank.

Fig. 1 gives absorbance curves of uranyl nitrate, ligand and uranium complexes at different pH values. The orange complex at pH 5.0 has an absorption peak at 370 nm and a flat region between 450 and 480 nm. With an increase in the pH of the solution, the colour of the complex becomes yellow and there is a shift in the absorption peak towards lower wave-length, thus indicating the change in the compositions of complexes with pH .

Fig 1 Absorbance curves Curve I- Reagent, 120 ppm, II- U(VI), 100 ppm, Remaining-uranium complexes at different pH (U 50 ppm).

Fig. 2 shows the effect of change of pH on absorbance measured at 370 nm. The pH for constant maximum absorbance for the orange complex is between 4.5 and 6.0. The increase in absorbance after pH 7.0 is due to the formation of yellow complex which has a higher absorbance at 370 nm than the orange complex.

FIG 2 EFFECT OF pH , 370 $m\mu$, U-25 P P M

Rate of reaction : The complete development of colour takes about 15 min. at room temperature and at 1 : 200 ratio of uranium to ligand. The orange complex is stable for 2 hr while the yellow complex is stable for 40 min. only.

Beer's law : The orange complex obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 10 to 50 ppm of uranium. The molecular extinction coefficient is 2.33×10^3 at 370 $m\mu$. The Sandell's sensitivity is determined as 0.071 γ/cm^2 .

Composition of the complexes : The molar compositions of uranium complexes were studied spectrophotometrically by applying Job's method of continuous variations¹². It was applied with two different concentrations, *viz.*, $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $4 \times 10^{-3} M$. In one set pH was maintained between 5 and 6 and in the other set between 8 and 9. Absorbance was measured at 370 nm for the orange complex and at 450 nm for the yellow complex. The results show that the orange complex is a mixture of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) and the yellow is 1 : 2.

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